

It would be our Fault

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Abstract

A single paragraph of about 200 words maximum. For research articles, abstracts should give a pertinent overview of the work. We strongly encourage authors to use the following style of structured abstracts, but without headings: (1) Background: Place the question addressed in a broad context and highlight the purpose of the study; (2) Methods: briefly describe the main methods or treatments applied; (3) Results: summarize the article's

Keywords: keyword 1; keyword 2; keyword 3 (List three to ten pertinent keywords specific to the article yet reasonably common within the subject discipline.)

1. Introduction

The Salt Lake Valley is an extremely delicate area, with extremely thin crust due to the stretch expansion zone beneath our feet, where the crust is being pulled apart in opposite directions, resulting in many small fault lines all along the valley. These faults, along with the Wasatch Fault Line are all prime generators of seismic activity, making it a waiting-game for the next seismic event which could be devastating to Salt Lake's residents and beyond. The following map of Utah shows clearly all the known fault lines in the state along with all the earthquakes Utah has experienced since 1980.

Figure 1. Haven Finley ArcGIS Earthquake Analysis

All the known fault lines in the state of Utah are marked in red while the recorded earthquakes are marked by the yellow circles with their size corresponding to the level of magnitude of each seismic event. When you zoom in to one of the most vulnerable areas

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along the great Wasatch Fault, the Brigham City area, the factors to consider become visible.

Figure 2. Wasatch Fault Analysis, Haven Finley 2025

Here, the Wasatch Fault is pointed out. The line continues on in the southern direction as it lines the Wasatch Mountains, however this line does not mean earthquakes can only occur on that line. The Wasatch Fault actually continues deep underground and stretches beyond the cities which exist in the region.

2. Materials and Methods

From this image, we can see how the fault also exists underneath our feet, meaning an earthquake focus point (the point at which it is generated from) can be farther out away from the mountains.

Figure 3. Utah Faults - Utah Geological Survey

Earthquakes in themselves are ultimately caused by the release of a pocket of energy which has built up over many years in a particular spot along a fault line such as

the point in the image. When the energy becomes too much to bear, and as the large chunks of rock move, the energy is released in the form of seismic waves. These seismic waves radiate outwards in all directions bringing massive amounts of destruction if the measured magnitude (M) is high enough.

The magnitude of an earthquake essentially means the amount of energy released from a specific stress point. Numerous pockets of energy like this are currently building up right beneath our feet in different locations along the fault. In the Salt Lake Valley, it is predicted that we will experience one or more seismic events of 6.73+ M in the next 50 years. Even if this great seismic event does not occur in the next 50 years, the energy in that focus point will continue to grow as more stress is applied. Meaning that as time goes on, when the earthquake does eventually happen, it will be an even larger magnitude than previously predicted.

The Salt Lake Valley is also at risk for another geological phenomenon called soil liquefaction which goes along with the intense earthquakes. Since this area was once an ancient sea as well as a large lake at one point in Earth's history, the ground we have built our cities on is primarily ancient sediments which are extremely thin, loose and fine-grained. Delicate sediments like this, especially ones with buildings built on top of them, can cause major damage when a seismic event occurs. When seismic waves travel through the water-saturated sediments, the shaking sensation causes the grains to become rearranged and break contact, creating spaces in which buildings and other structures can sink into.

3. Results

The Salt Lake Valley is also at risk for another geological phenomenon called soil liquefaction which goes along with the intense earthquakes. Since this area was once an ancient sea as well as a large lake at one point in Earth's history, the ground we have built our cities on is primarily ancient sediments which are extremely thin, loose and fine-grained. Delicate sediments like this, especially ones with buildings built on top of them, can cause major damage when a seismic event occurs. When seismic waves travel through the water-saturated sediments, the shaking sensation causes the grains to become rearranged and break contact, creating spaces in which buildings and other structures can sink into.

Figure 4. Guide to Soil Liquefaction - Applied Earth Science

Additionally, with this shaking sensation of the sediments, these types of loose soils can also amplify certain earthquake wave frequencies. If these specific frequencies mirror the frequency of the buildings or other structures, the shaking intensifies and prolongs, resulting in greater damage.

Figure 5. Earthquake Hazard Maps & Liquefaction - earthscope ANGLE

All things considered, this area within Utah is extremely vulnerable due to the amount of geologic activity occurring just beneath our feet. Building cities on top of this area that are not properly earthquake proof is a dangerous game and a major risk to the safety of the residents of the valley. If we continue on this path of not proper preparedness, the lasting effects of the awaiting seismic event would be our fault.

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Conflicts of Interest

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